

Continuous nursing care for patients with cervical cancer in the community

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Abstract

In Cuba, approximately 600 women die each year from cervical cancer; these figures express the number of deaths, but not really the incidence of the disease. From the diagnosis of the disease, the nursing staff plays a leading role in the care of these patients. Continuous care aims to give patients comprehensive, biopsychosocial and spiritual care, at all levels and during all phases of the disease. The cervical cancer constitutes one of the entities with the greatest impact and repercussion on women's health, especially among young women.

Keywords: Continuous nursing care; Cervical cancer; Community; Women

1. Introduction

In Cuba, approximately 600 women die each year from cervical cancer (CCU); these figures express the number of deaths, but not really the incidence of the disease, since not every woman who suffers from it dies from it⁽¹⁾. The nurse is a vital support in the care of every patient, in the case of women with CCU they are of the utmost importance.

The nursing staff covers a wide field of action in the face of the difficult process that women with this disease and their families go through. They contribute continuously and decisively from the initial stage of the diagnosis news, during the various treatment situations, and on some occasions until death⁽²⁾.

Kristen M. Swanson, defines the importance of nursing care by the rapport that is achieved between it and the patient.⁽³⁾ Nursing staff must understand the meaning of an event in another's life, avoiding conjectures, focusing on the person being cared for, looking for clues, meticulously evaluating and seeking a compromise process between the one who cares and the one who is cared for⁽³⁾.

When talking about health care, in this case of women with CC, it is accepted that the nursing staff seek different measures and ways to care for and maintain them⁽⁴⁾. This constitutes one of the health events of notable importance for the control, prevention, cure and care of women with chronic non-communicable diseases.

In community care, the foundation is necessary from the theoretical and practical perspective of innovative interventions for the management of continuous nursing care and its influence as a strength in the processes of the diagnosis of CC⁽⁵⁾. At each stage of the disease, the nursing staff must have defined the care to be developed.

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2. Dear Editor

Human papilloma virus (HPV) infection is the etiological factor considered in CC. This relates to sexual behavior in a direct and proportional way⁽⁶⁾.

There are four phases in the development of CC: HPV infection of the metaplastic epithelium in the transformation zone, its viral persistence, the clonal progression of the persistently infected epithelium to precancerous lesions, and the invasion through the basement membrane of the epithelium.⁽⁷⁾ Risk factors are associated with the onset of sexual relations at an early age, multiple sexual partners, a history of sexually transmitted diseases, and the high number of sexual partners of the male partner⁽⁷⁾.

There are other external and characteristic collateral factors of the host that are involved in the development of oncogenesis. Some of these factors are permanent viral infection; genetic predisposition; being a carrier of HIV is related to a five times greater risk; nutrition deficit; environmental factors, among others⁽⁸⁾.

From the diagnosis of the disease, the nursing staff plays a leading role in the care of these patients. Those affected go through multiple stages of treatment that range from simple procedures to the most radical surgery and palliative care. In each of them, the necessary care, which includes physical and emotional support, is of essential value.

Continuous care aims to give patients comprehensive, biopsychosocial and spiritual care, at all levels and during all phases of the disease. It should not only be seeking the best treatment, it is necessary to give priority to the quality of life of the patient⁽⁹⁾.

Maintaining continuous care of the patient can achieve greater survival and a better response to treatment of the disease in general⁽⁹⁾. These patients need to feel safe, to have someone to hold on to, to trust in to show that they are still productive, that they are part of a group, receive affection and have human contact⁽¹⁰⁾.

Nursing staff will have to maintain a perfect balance between the scientific and the humanistic. They have to promote behaviors in patients to cope with and overcome their condition given by the disease, improve their quality of life and, when the time comes, guarantee them a dignified death⁽¹¹⁾.

In the opinion of the authors, the nurse, as the person responsible for the care of the patient, should be attentive to the patient's health problems. It implies the nurse's ability to perceive and identify the patient's needs (biopsychosocial and spiritual) and respond to them holistically, even before they express them.

It is the responsibility of the nurse to create physical and human conditions favorable to the well-being of the patient, these are related to their self-care, communication and collaboration, promoting a necessary environment for their speedy recovery. This is achieved with continuous nursing care effectively.

The author considers that continuous nursing care for women with CC is the construction of knowledge that favors caring for women with CC in an integral way, at all levels and during all phases of the disease, which implies caring for the patient from a biological, psychological, family, work and social point of view.

The CCU constitutes one of the entities with the greatest impact and repercussion on women's health, especially among young women. It has been considered an emerging disease for a few years.

Many professionals do not have sufficient information about the disease and how to apply their continuous care, which is why a process of continuous training is required, in order to be up to the task that the epidemiological circumstances require. The CC brings with it social, human and economic consequences. It constitutes a major problem in community care and humanity.

3. Conclusion

The CCU constitutes one of the entities with the greatest impact and repercussion on women's health, especially among young women. It has been considered an emerging disease for a few years. Many professionals do not have sufficient information about the disease and how to apply their continuous care, which is why a process of continuous training is required, in order to be up to the task that the epidemiological circumstances require. The CC brings with it social, human and economic consequences. It constitutes a major problem in community care and humanity.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

Author's contribution

Rodríguez Mateo M and González Pérez RB: Conception or design of the work. Data collection. Data analysis and interpretation. Drafting the article. Final approval of the version to be published.

Concepción Pacheco JA, Ávila Sánchez M, Naranjo Hernández Y: Data analysis and interpretation. Critical revision of the article. Final approval of the version to be published

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